

**MAHMUD QOSHG'ARIYNING «DEVONU LUG'OTIT TURK»
ASARI – ILMIY AHAMIYATLI ME'ROS**

Bobojonova Dilnoza Oxunjonovna

Osiyo xalqaro universiteti

“Tarix va filologiya” kafedrası o'qituvchisi

E-mail: bobojonovadilnozaoxunjonovna@oxu.uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10395723>

Annotatsiya. Mahmud Qoshg'ariyning «Devonu lug'otit turk» asari o'zbek tili tarixida yaratilgan asarlar orasida o'zining ilmiy qiymatiga ko'ra alohida ajralib turadi. Olim bu asar ustida uzoq yillar ishladi, ko'p yillar yurtma-yurt kezib material to'pladi, turkiylar yashagan keng va katta hududni birma-bir kezib chiqdi, urug'lar, qabilalar, xalqlarning turmush tarzini, urf-odatlarini, kasb-korlarini, turar joylarini, nufuzlarini aniqladi va ularning tillariga xos xususiyatlarni sinchiklab o'rgandi.

Kalit so'zlar: maqol, janr, poetik, tabiat, poeziya, xalq ijodi, badiiy-tarixiy solnoma, jumboq va muammolar, urf-odat.

**MAHMUD KASHGARI'S WORK "DEVONU LUG'OTIT TURK" IS AN
IMPORTANT SCIENTIFIC HERITAGE**

Abstract. Mahmud Kashgari's work "Devonu lug'otit Turk" stands out among the works created in the history of the Uzbek language due to its scientific value. The scientist worked on this work for many years, traveled around the country and collected material for many years, traveled one by one to the vast and large territory inhabited by the Turks, determined the lifestyles, customs, professions, residences, and influence of the clans, tribes, peoples. and carefully studied the peculiarities of their languages.

Key words: proverb, genre, poetic, nature, poetry, folk art, art-historical annals, riddles and problems, tradition.

**ТРУД МАХМУДА КАШГАРИ «ДЕВОНУ ЛУГОТИТ ТЮРК» ЯВЛЯЕТСЯ
ВАЖНЫМ НАУЧНЫМ НАСЛЕДИЕМ.**

Аннотация. Среди произведений, созданных в истории узбекского языка, своей научной ценностью выделяется труд Махмуда Кашгари «Девону луготит тюрк». Ученый много лет работал над этой работой, много лет путешествовал по стране и собирал материал, объездил один за другим обширную и обширную территорию, населенную тюрками, определил образ жизни, обычаи, профессии, места жительства, влияние тюрков. роды, племена, народы и тщательно изучали особенности их языков.

Ключевые слова: пословица, жанр, поэтика, природа, поэзия, народное творчество, искусствоведческая летопись, загадки и проблемы, традиция.

Mahmud Qoshg'ariy buning natijasida turkiy qabilalarning deyarli barchasini va ularning tillarini juda puxta, mukammal aniqlashga muvaffaq bo'ldi. Har bir so'zning qaysi qabilaga tegishli ekanini, so'zlarning ma'no va shakl xususiyatlarini, ularning qadimgi va hozirgi variantlarini, qabilalar tilidagi so'zlar talaffuzidagi moslik va farqlarni har tomonlama aniqlab chiqdi. O'z fikrini dalillash uchun xalq qo'shiqlari va maqollaridan keng foydalandi.

O'zbek tili taraqqiyotida o'ziga xos ahamiyatga ega bu asar Basim Atalay, V.V.Bartol'd, A.N.Samoylovich, P.K.Juz'be, S.E.Malov, Andrey Nikolaevich Kononov, Aleksandr Konstantinovich Borovkov, N.A.Baskakov kabi chet el olimlari va Abdurauf Fitrat, Solih Mutallibov, Natan Mallaev, G'ani Abdurahmonov, Hamid Ne'matov kabi o'zbek tilshunoslari tomonidan ma'lum darajada tadqiq etilgan.

Ma'lumki, «Devonu lug'otit turk» asarining qo'lyozmasi 1914 yilda Turkiyaning Diyorbakir shahrida topiladi. Asarning bu qo'lyozmasi Mahmud Qoshg'ariy o'zi yozgan nusxadan — asl nusxadan ko'chirilgan. Bu kitobni ko'chiruvchi xattot Muhammad bin Abu Bakr ibn Abdul Fotih al Soviy al Damashqi'dir. Bu nusxa «Devonu lug'otit turk» yozilgandan so'ng salkam 200 yil o'tgach, ya'ni 1266 yilda ko'chirilgan. Qo'lyozma 319 varaqli katta bir jilddan iborat bo'lib, varaqlari tarqoq, yirtiq, boshi oxiri noma'lum, sahifalari qo'yilmagan. Hozir u Istanbulda, Fotih kutubxonasining Ali Amiriy fondida saqlanmoqda. Diyorbakirlik kekxa kitob muxlislaridan Ali Amiriy mazkur asarni shu yili fan olamiga ma'lum qiladi.

«Devonu lug'otit turk» qo'lyozmasi uchga bo'linib, birinchi va ikkinchi jildlari 1915 yilda, uchinchi jildi 1917 yilda Istanbulda Kilisli Rifat muharrirligida nashr etildi. Tilshunos Bosim Atalay asarni turk tiliga birinchi bo'lib mu-kammal tarjima qildi. Asarning uchala tomi 1939-1941 yillarda nashr etildi. Basim Atalay «Devonu lug'otit turk»ni turk tiliga birinchi bo'lib mukammal tarjima qilibgina qolmay, uni har tomonlama ilmiy jihatdan tekshirgan, Koshg'ariy ijodini tinmay targ'ib qilgan olimdir.

Abdulahad Nuriy «Devonu lug'otit turk»dagi aforizm va maqollarning 251 tasini to'plab, «O'talar so'zi» nomi ostida nashr ettirdi. Shokir Ulkutoshirning «Qashg'arli Mahmud» nomli kichik bir asarida Mahmud Koshg'ariyning hayoti, ijodi va «Devonu lug'otit turk»ning mazmuni bayon etilgan.

G'arbiy Yevropada sharqshunos olim Karl Brokkel'man 1920 yilda «Devonu lug'otit turk» to'g'risida birinchi maqolasini e'lon qildi, keyinchalik asardagi so'z, ism va joy nomlarining ro'yxatini tuzib, qaysi tom va sahifasini belgilab, alohida kitob (ko'rsatkich) tarzida nemischa so'z boshisi bilan 1928 yilda nashr ettirdi; «Devonu lug'otit turk»ning til va adabiyot uchun ahamiyati, uning tarjimasi to'g'risida ham bir necha maqolalar yozdi.

Atoqli turkolog Sergey Malov Toshkentda ishlagan davrida ham, keyinchalik ham «Devonu lug'otit turk»ga katta ahamiyat berdi. Uning «Qadimgi turkiy yozuv yodgorliklari» nomli monografiyasida asarga oid qimmatli fikrlar ifodalangan va kattagina bibliografiya berilgan.

Sharqshunos P.K.Juz'be 1926-1928 yillarda «Devonu lug'otit turk»ga bag'ishlab ikkita maqola yozdi. P.K.Juz'be asli falastinlik arab bo'lib, u 1871 yilda tug'ilgan. Qozon universitetida ta'lim olgan, Qozonda va Bokuda professorlik qilgan, 1942 yilda Bokuda vafot etgan. U maqolalarida «Devonu lug'otit turk» asariga juda yuksak baho berdi, uning katta ahamiyatini uqtirib o'tdi. U yozadi: «Mahmudning «Devonu lug'otit turk» asarida o'sha vaqtda Qoraxoniylar davlati tarkibiga kirgan Shimoliy-Sharqiy qabilalarning deyarli hammasi to'plangan. Dadil aytish mumkinki, yaqindagina (XIX asr oxirlarida) Rossiyada va Sharqda o'rganilgan turkiy tillar fonetikasi va etimologiyasining asosiy qonunlari XI asrdayoq Mahmud tomonidan aniqlangan va o'rganilgan edi. Mahmudning bu tekshirishlari shu qadar keng va chuqurki, hatto, bunday asar XIX asrda yozilganda ham unga shon-sharaf bo'lardi. Mahmud Qoshg'ariyning

«Devonu lug'otit turk»i singari asar fan olamida keyingi asrlarda ham yaratilgan emas. Uning asari bamisoli «Turkiy qomus»dir».

O'zbek olimlari orasida «Devonu lug'otit turk» asarini ilmiy asosda o'rganishni Turkiston jadidchilik harakatining g'oyaviy rahnamosi Abdurauf Fitrat boshlab berdi. Uning «Devonu lug'otit turk» asariga oid tadqiqotlaridan biri «Eng eski turk adabiyoti namunalari» deb nomlanadi. Mazkur tadqiqot-majmua 1927 yilda isloh qilingan arab yozuvida chop etilgan bo'lib, unda Fitrat turkshunoslik ilmining asoschisi Mahmud Qoshg'ariyning mashhur «Devonu lug'otit turk» asaridagi she'riy parchalarni yig'ib, ularni adabiy tur va janrlarga ko'ra tasniflagan. «Bir-ikki so'z» deb nomlangan so'z boshida o'zbek tili va adabiyoti tarixi, turkiy tilshunoslik va o'zbek adabiyotshunosligi uchun muhim, ahamiyatli fikrlar ifodalangan. Ular jumlasiga quyidagilarni aytish mumkin:

a) Mahmud Qoshg'ariy, V.V.Radlov va A.N.Samoylovichlarning turkiy tillar tasnifiga oid ilmiy qarashlari mufassal tahlil etilgan;

b) yangi o'zbek adabiy tilining asosiy manbalari to'g'ri belgilangan;

v) «Devonu lug'otit turk» asaridagi she'riy parchalar adabiy tur va janrlarga ko'ra aniq tasniflangan;

g) «Devonu lug'otit turk» asarining ilmiy-tarixiy ahamiyatiga to'g'ri baho berilgan.

Yuqorida aytib o'tilganidek, «Devonu lug'otit turk» asarining qo'lyozmasi 1914 yilda Turkiyaning Diyorbakir shahrida topiladi, 319 sahifali bu qo'lyozmaning fotonusxasini Kilisli Rifat 1915-1917 yillarda uch tomdan iborat qilib, Istanbulda nashr ettiradi. Fitrat ushbu nashrdan foydalanib, uni tadqiq etishga harakat qilgan. Dastlab u turkshunoslar Mahmud Koshg'ariy, V.V.Radlov va A.N.Samoylovichning turkiy tillar tasniflariga o'z munosabatini bildirib o'tadi.

Ma'lumki, V.V.Radlov tasnifida, asosan, hududiy-geografik nuqtai nazar asos qilib olingan va shunga ko'ra turkiy tillar to'rt guruhga bo'lingan. Ular quyidagilardir: 1. Sharqiy guruh (Bu guruhga oltoy, chulim, xakas, shor, tuva va enasoy turklarining tili kiradi). 2. G'arbiy guruh (Bu guruhga qirg'iz, qozoq, qoraqalpoq, tatar, boshqird tillari kiradi). 3. O'rta Osiyo guruhi (Bu guruhga uyg'ur va o'zbek tillari kiradi). 4. Janubiy guruh (Bu guruhga turkman, ozarbayjon va turk tillari kiradi).

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